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Current Stem Cell Clinical Trials and Research Progress

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Abstract

During the last 15-10 years, the interest in stem cells has been growing exponentially because of their self-renewal abilities and high plasticity. The physiologic function of adult stem cells (ASCs) is maintaining tissue homeostasis through cellular damaged or aged turn over, while embryonic stem cells (ESCs) generate all committed cell type of organism. Researchers try to exploit these properties to treat degenerative pathologies, as neurological disorder (Parkinson, Alzheimer, Ataxias, multiple sclerosis...), musculoskeletal disorder (arthrosis, dystrophy, heart failure...), diabetes, eyes disorder (optical nerve or corneal degeneration...), autoimmune disease, renal failure and cancer. Although initial enthusiasm for them potentiality, SCs therapy tire to develop for several reasons. Firstly, self renewal and plasticity are also properties of cancer cells and the possibility to lose control on transplanted SCs could become the worst side effect obtainable.

Secondly, in case of allergenic graft will avoid immunorejection by the recipient. Finally, to have ESCs is necessary to manipulate and to sacrifice embryos and scientific, but above all catholic, world identify in this stage of develop a human with same rights of a born man. In this review, we report on recent advances on the clinical trial about stem cells (SCs) therapy. Ours intention is to show all stem cells types disposable and them rational employment in medicine, with focus on treatment benefits and side effects.

To give an ethical imprint at the work, we resume the more common clinical practice guidelines in a work track.

Keywords: *Stem cell, Research , Therapies, Progress*

Stem cells

Stem cells are the basic building blocks of the body. SCs are undifferentiated cells capable of self-renewal and differentiation into diverse mature progenies.

Table-1 summarizes stem cell cardinal characteristics [1-12]. SCs play a central role in tissue genesis, regeneration and homeostasis by providing new elements to increase tissue mass during pre- and post-natal growth, and replacing cell loss due to senescence or damage [8, 9].

Natural stem cells

Stem cell begins with the most primitive totipotent stem cell, the zygote, which is the result of the fusion of two germ cells (oocyte and sperm) during the process of fertilization. As a totipotent stem cell, the zygote is able to give rise to both the embryo and the placenta. The “artificial” counterpart of the totipotent zygote is referred to as a clonote and can be created in the laboratory with an experimental approach known as somatic nuclear transfer, involving removal of the nucleus from a somatic cell and its insertion/ transfer into an enucleated oocyte [13]. The first blastomers that derive from the first division of the zygote or clonote are still totipotent stem cells. In support of this is the well-known fact that the first blastomers, if separated from each other, can give rise

to two independent embryos [14], as seen in the case of monozygotic siblings. When the blastomers have divided into the 32-cell stage, the embryo is known as a morula. Cells which form the morula have already lost their totipotency and are now pluripotent. The pluripotent stem cell (PSC) is defined as being able to contribute to the development of the embryo but has lost the capacity to form the trophoblast (which gives rise to the placenta). Thus the term PSC refers to the stem cells that contribute to all three germ layers, mesoderm, ectoderm and endoderm, but not to the trophoblast.

During early embryogenesis, the growing morula develops a central cavity and becomes the blastocyst [15]. A fully developed blastocyst contains cells that are precursors for extra-embryonic tissues and a distinct group of cells called the inner cell mass (ICM) [16]. The cells of the ICM are also pluripotent and can give rise to all three germ layers of the developing embryo [17].

Stem cell types

Exist an huge variety of stem cells: from pluripotent ESCs, isolated from inner cell masses (ICMs) of blastocysts, and multipotent umbilical cord stem cells (UCSCs), which appear to derive from amniotic membrane epithelium, to ASCs, localized in specific niches or tissue compartment as bone marrow (BM), brain, skin, eyes, hearth, kidneys, lungs, gastrointestinal tract, pancreas, liver, breast, ovaries, prostate and testis. However, the two basic types of stem cells are: embryonic stem cells that are isolated from the inner cell mass of blastocysts, and adult somatic stem cells that are found in adult tissues [18-20].

Embryonic stem cell lines (ES cell lines) are cultures of cells derived from the epiblast tissue of the inner cell mass (ICM) of a blastocyst or earlier morula stage embryos. A blastocyst is an early stage embryo—approximately four to five days old in humans and consisting of 50–150 cells. Blastocysts are pre-implantation stage embryos approximately 1 week in age depending on species. From the ICMs develop the organism, whereas the surrounding trophectoderm contribute to the placental chorion. ES cells are pluripotent and give rise during development to all derivatives of the three primary germ layers: ectoderm, endoderm and mesoderm. In other words, they can develop into each of the more than 200 cell types of the adult body when given sufficient and necessary stimulation for a specific cell type. They do not contribute to the extra-embryonic membranes or the placenta. Fetal stem cells are primitive cell types found in the organs of fetuses ESCs could be isolated

using physical microdissection or through compliment-mediated immunodissection. The ICM cells are difficult to maintain in culture. To obtain continuous culture derived from ICM cells needs of feeder layer of primary fibroblast cells that synthesize factor able to maintain undifferentiated ESCs. This method requires pretreatment to block replication of feeder layer cells and continuous supply of sustaining cells. ESCs could be maintained in culture for prolonged time (1-2 years), in undifferentiated phenotype and this is an advantage for therapeutic and research applications [12, 21].

Adult stem cells ASCs are cells localized in specific organism niches and help in maintaining homeostasis of the tissue/organs. At the end of embryogenesis, each tissue contains a heterogeneous population of cells at different stages of maturation, including relatively undifferentiated, self-renewing cells, termed adult SCs (ASCs). ASCs have a limited differentiation potential and are responsible for turnover and repair within the tissue of origin. ASCs have been identified in several organs, such as bone marrow (BM), gastrointestinal epithelium, skin, brain, muscle, and liver [11, 22, 23]. The term adult stem cell refers to any cell which is found in a developed organism that has two properties: the ability to divide and create another cell like itself and also divide and create a cell more differentiated than itself. Also known as somatic stem cells and germ line (giving rise to gametes) stem cells, they can be found in children, as well as adults [24, 25]. In adult organisms, stem cells and progenitor cells act as a repair system for the body, replenishing specialized cells, but also maintain the normal turnover of regenerative organs, such as blood, skin, or intestinal tissues. The reciprocal interactions between SCs and their niche influence SC behavior: a complex network of developing signals regulates the balance between quiescence and the dividing state, leading ASCs toward self-renewal or differentiation [26-29].

Researchers found ASCs in BM, heart, kidney, brain, skin, eyes, gastrointestinal tract, breast, ovaries, prostate and testis. ASCs originate during ontogeny and remain in specific area where they stay in quiescent state for variable time. They have a restricted differentiation potential, originating a limited number of distinct cell progenitors. In niches microenvironment reciprocal cell interaction and chemical dialogue between stem cells and stromal cell regulate ASCs self-renewal and differentiation.

Between ASCs different type, more interesting attention have had BMCs, HSCs, adipose tissue-derived

stromal cells (ADSCs) and derived MSCs. MSCs are adult stem cells derived from bone marrow, liver, umbilical cord, placenta, adipose tissue, synovial membrane, amniotic fluid and teeth. They are generally restricted to forming only mesoderm-specific cell types such as adipocytes, osteoblasts, myocytes and chondrocytes, but several MSCs are able to form all three embryonic germ layers. Adipose tissue contain a particular type of MSCs. ASCs display a similar gene expression profile and surface antigen phenotype to bone marrow-derived MSCs, such as CD34 and CD44, acquire a similar fibroblast morphology. Nevertheless, ASCs express also non BM specific marker, such as VCAM-1 and NGFR. Furthermore, ASCs differentiate primarily to mesoderm tissue in vitro and in vivo could repair bone tissue and reconstitute immune system, but also are able to differentiate in endothelial cell and contribute to revascularization of ischemic tissue. HSCs derived prevalently from BM, in particular near endosteal bone surface and sinusoidal endothelium, and in a little part circulate in peripheral blood. The interest for these SCs depends to relatively easy extraction of BM from the donor or less invasive, but less efficacy, stimulation of releasing in peripheral blood after treatment with granulocyte-colony stimulating factor (G-CSF). Identification and isolation of HSCs is possible with antibody anti-CD34, a surface protein that distinguishes SCs from other hematopoietic cells [11, 29].

According to the hierarchical model, long-term SCs (true SCs, extremely rare, with high differentiation potential and proliferative capacity) can give rise to short-term SCs (transit-amplifying or committed progenitors), which in turn are able to differentiate into mature elements providing tissue-specific functions [8,30]. Despite the paradigm of unidirectional cell determination, recent studies have shown that ASCs are endowed with an unexpected plasticity, as circulating adult progenitor cells can differentiate into mature cells of other tissue types [21, 26, 31]. A particularly high degree of plasticity is shown by bone marrow SCs (BM-SCs), which in vivo and in vitro studies have proved to be able to differentiate into a wide range of non-hematopoietic phenotypes [32-35]. It has also been demonstrated that BM-SCs normally circulate in the peripheral blood, and that the number of circulating SCs committed toward neuronal and hepatic differentiation increases following treatment with mobilizing agents [36]. This phenomenon has led to speculation about the existence of BM-derived pluripotent SCs, which could migrate from the peripheral blood into various tissues and contribute to

normal turnover and repair following injury [8, 28, 37]. Several types of stem cells recently identified in adult tissues, mainly bone marrow (BM) or cord blood (CB). These cells possess differentiation potential into cells from more than one germ layer. These cells were described as MSC - mesenchymal stem cells, MAPC - multipotent adult progenitor cells, MIAMI - marrow isolated adult multi-lineage inducible cells or MASC- Multipotent Adult non-hematopoietic stem cells that were detected by different investigators using different experimental strategies.

Umbilical cord stem cells UCSCs are multipotent cells that might generate diverse differentiated cell types, localized in umbilical cord epithelium (UCE, derived from amniotic membrane epithelium) and umbilical cord blood (UCB). If cultured on fibroblast-populated collagen gel, UCE cells can differentiate in keratinocyte-like cells and to generate stratified epithelial structure when grafted onto the back of nude mice. UCB, instead, contains primitive subpopulation of CD34⁺ hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) and mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), able to differentiate into multiple lineages.

Stem cell research

Although the concept of stem cells was introduced nearly a century ago by Alexander Maximow [38], Modern stem-cell research began in 1963 when Canadian scientists James E Till, Ernest A McCullough and Lou Siminovitsh established assays to detect hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) [2]. Those scientists found HSCs in the bone marrow of mice. In a series of experiments they demonstrated that cells from the bone marrow could reconstitute hematopoietic and hence rescue lethally irradiated animals. Using serial transplantations, they established the self-renewal ability of the original bone marrow cells. When cells from splenic colonies in the first recipients of bone marrow transplants were further transplanted into other animals that had received a lethal dose of irradiation, colonies of white and red blood corpuscles were found in the secondary recipients. On the basis of these experiments, they defined HSCs as cells that have "the abilities of unrestricted self-renewal as well as multi-lineage differentiation" [2]. This discovery marked the beginning of modern-day stem-cell research. Only in recent years have other somatic stem cells been identified in tissues with more limited regenerative capacity [18, 23].

Table (1):Stem cell characteristics	
<p>1-Self-renewal through mitotic cell division. The ability to go through numerous cycles of cell division while maintaining the undifferentiated state. SCs are thought to alternate symmetric and asymmetric divisions, hence maintaining the property of self-renewal [10].</p> <p>2-SCs possess a hierarchy of potentialities: from the totipotency of the zygote and its immediate progeny, to the pluripotency of embryonic SCs (ESCs), and the multi/unipotency of adult SCs (ASCs) [8, 11, 12].</p> <p>Potency - the capacity to differentiate into a diverse range of specialized cell types. Stem cells to be either totipotent or pluripotent.</p> <p>A-Totipotent (omnipotent) stem cells can differentiate into embryonic and extra-embryonic cell types and form complete organism.</p> <p>B-Pluripotent stem cells can differentiate into nearly all cells i.e. cells derived from any of the three germ layers.</p> <p>Multipotent stem cells can differentiate into a number of cells, but only those of a closely related family of cells.</p> <p>Oligopotent stem cells can differentiate into only a few cells, such as lymphoid or myeloid stem cells.</p> <p>Unipotent cells can produce only one cell type, their own, but have the property of self-renewal which distinguishes them from non-stem cells (e.g. muscle stem cells)[1-7].</p>	
In Vitro characteristics	
<p>1-Able in vitro cultures to give rise to more differentiated stem cells committed to cells from all three germ layers.</p> <p>2 Pluripotentiality which is in vivo contribution to blastocyst development. Accordingly, PSC if injected/aggregated with cells from inner cell mass of the blastocyst should be able to give rise to cells from all three germ layers (meso-, endo-, and ecto-derm) including gametes.</p> <p>3- Tertraploid complementation potential: PSC could give rise to a whole embryo. For example if PSC is transduced with gene encoding with green fluorescence protein (GFP) it will give rise to GFP+ chimera (blastocyst complementation) or GFP+ mouse (Tertraploid complementation).</p>	

Disorder	Trials summary
Rheumatoid arthritis (RA)	Snowden et al [54] treated 76 patients with severe RA resistant to conventional therapies with AHST. Treatment in the majority obviated the need for antirheumatic drugs sensitivity. One patient submitted to graft purification and immunosuppression died.
Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is associated with marked reduction of number and proliferative capability of HSCs. CD34+ present an elevate apoptosis rate. AHST reduced the number of apoptotic CD34+ pre-treatment.	50 patients with SLE refractory to standard immunosuppressive therapies and have either organ or life threatening visceral involvement were treated with AHST and were followed for 5 years. About 50% of patients experienced disease-free survive. HSCinfusion ameliorate disease activity, improved serologic marker and either stabilize or reverse organ dysfunction, but is associated to a high relapse rate and mortality remained high (23%)[55]. Traynor et al [56] conducted a single centre trial on AHST transplant in 15 patients with SLE. General outcome was better and only 2 subjects had recurrence of symptoms
Multiple sclerosis (MS) Mezey et al hypothesize that HSC-derived cells could replace damage neurons [60]	76 patients with MS not responding to conventional therapies were treated with AHST. Better results were obtained in patients with secondary progressive MS (SPMS) and less than 40 years old. Cell therapy reduced inflammation in the CNS, 8 cases experienced neurological deterioration during the treatment, 5 patients died of post-operative infections or localized toxicity [57]. Poor effectiveness of AHST was observed on 26 patients with primary progressive MS (PPMS); only one had clinical improvement, 13 subjects remained stable and in 7 patients there was deterioration. 4 subjects showed at MRI new lesions [59].
Systemic sclerosis (SSc) AHST may improve skin flexibility& stabilize pulmonary involvement [61-71]. However, disease progression & treatment complication) are associated to high mortality rates (27%) [72].	57 patients with SSc were treated with HSTC & followed up for more than 6 months. 14 patients achieved complete remission and 32 achieved partial remission, for a period of over 3 years. Some patients were in better clinical condition than before treatment. In a multi-center study on 11 patients, 5 patients showed reactivation of SSc after AHST, but the treatment extended the short life expectancy of patients with severe SS [73]
Crohn's disease	Severe refractory Crohn's disease were treated with cyclophosphamide (CY) and G-CSF and then with AHST. All patients didn't show serious infection toxicity at 2-30 months of follow-up; even they clinically remitted with disappearance of diarrhea, reduction of abdominal pain and activity [74, 75].
Autoimmune thrombocytopenic purpura (AITP)	AITP cases are responsive to high doses of immunosuppressors with myelosuppression risks. HSTC demonstrates to accelerate reestablishment of the hematological parameters while reduce the number of autoimmune cells in the body 12 cases of AITP were treated with AHST. The responses varying from transient response to continuous remission or even death related to transplantation [76]. 14 patients with chronic refractory AITP treated with CY and AHST, 8 obtain a durable response, suggesting that SC accelerated hematological reestablishment [77].
Autoimmune hemolytic anemia (AIHA)	AHST treatment as associated with immunosuppressive therapy could be an effective treatment for AIHA [78, 79].

Disorder	Trials Summary
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<p>Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) . At present, all treatment designed doesn't restore neural cells. Stem cell therapy can be a promising strategy could combine neuroprotection with recover neuromotor function.</p>	<p>Intrathecal injection of selected HSC into spinal zone in 3 patients with severe ALS afforded partial improvement on neurological function, without complication [80]. 7 patients with severe impairment of the lower limb without respiratory complication were treated with spinal injection (T7-T9 level) of ex vivo expanded AHSC extracted from BM. Most of the patients experienced slight and reversible effects, as intercostals pain or dysesthesia, persisting after 2 years follow up. General deceleration in loss of muscular strength in the legs (marked in 4 patients and slight in 2) and in decline of respiratory function (4 patients) were observed [81]. 61 patients with ALS at different stages received SCs extracted from 4- 8 week embryos. Improvement of neurological function was observed in 34% after 2 months mostly in early stage disease cases [82].</p>
<p>Diabetes Mellitus (DM) Type I diabetes SC transplantation could rehabilitate pancreatic islets and reintroduce physiological secretion of human insulin. Allogenic islet transplantation (AIT) has also been tried [85].</p>	<p>15 patients with newly diagnosed type 1 DM (aged 14-31 years) were treated with AHST. Culture-negative bilateral pneumonia was observed in 1 patient and late endocrine dysfunction in 2 others). AHST improved β-cells function in all but 1 patient and induced prolonged (18.8 months) mean insulin independence in the majority of the subjects [83]. 1 month after single transplantation of pancreatic islets from non-heart-beating donors or a living donor, 6 patients with DM showed metabolic stability, sufficient to avoid life-threatening severe hypoglycemia and prevent or delay the progress of secondary complication of diabetes [84]. An interesting study transplant a combination of different stem cell type in insulinopenic DM patients. 5 subjects were submitted to allotropic human adipose-tissue-derived, insulin-making mesenchymal stem cells (h-AD-MSC) transfusion with unfractionated cultured bone marrow. In all patients, insulin requirements decreased (from 30% to 50%) and serum c-peptide levels increased (from 4- to 26-fold) with a mean follow up of 2.9 months. The practice was safety and no side effects appear during follow up [86].</p>
<p>Spinal cord lesions</p>	<p>In a Korean phase I/II clinical trial, 35 complete spinal cord injury patients were divided in 2 groups to compare the effects of autologous BMC transplantation after GM-CSF stimulation. Furthermore, to evaluate if efficacy of transplantation correlated with time of injection after the trauma, BMCs-treating group was distributed in three subgroups: acute (<2weeks), subacute (2-8weeks) and chronic (>8 weeks). No significant neuropathic pain was observed. About 30% of acute and subacute treatment groups showed neurological improvements passing to ASIA A score to B or C [96].</p>

Disorder	Trails Summary
<p>Parkinson's disease (PD) characterized by the selective and gradual loss of nigrostriatal dopamine-containing neurons loss of pigmented dopamine-secreting (dopaminergic) cells in the pars compacta region of the substantia nigra. [87, 88].</p>	<p>6 patients with PD received implants of human embryonic mesencephalic tissue unilaterally in the striatum. Every patient was previously engrafted with tissue from 4 to 8 donors into the putamen (4 patients) or the putamen plus the caudate nucleus (1 patient) on the other side. Dopa level increased after 12-18 months. After the second graft, 2 patients exhibited marked improvements, as virtual disappear of 'on-off' fluctuations, increase speed movement and L-dopa reduction. The improvement in 1 patient was moderate. 2 patients experienced worsening [89]. 6 patients with advanced PD were treated with bilateral fetal nigral transplantation from donors aged 6.5 to 9 weeks after conception. Surgery complications were mild and transient. Treatment was safe & associated with significant improvements of daily living activities and motor function [90]. 5 patients with PD were transplanted bilaterally into the putamen and caudate nucleus with human embryonic mesencephalic tissue from donors. In the second postoperative year, mean daily L-dopa uptake was decreased by 54% and UPDRS score in 'off' phase was decreased by a mean of 40%. Dopa detection with PET showed a mean 61% increase in the putamen, and 24% increase in the caudate nucleus, compared with preoperative values [91]. A double-blind randomly trial compared transplant of cultured mesencephalic tissue derived from embryos with sham surgery. In 17 of the 20 patients fiber outgrowth from the implanted neurons, as indicated by an increase in F-fluorodopa uptake on PET or postmortem examination. However improvements of first year, dystonia and dyskinesias recurred in 15% of the patients who received transplants [92]. An American double-blind trial compared fetal nigral transplantation with placebo. 34 patients with PD were treated and followed for 24 month. There was no significant treatment effect. Although striatal fluorodopa uptake increased, 56% of transplanted patients developed dyskinesia that persisted after dopaminergic medication [93].</p>
<p>Spinal cord lesions There is no cure for spinal trauma. However, interesting results were obtained with stem cells transplantation [87].</p>	<p>7 patients with spinal cord injury (American Spinal Injury Association [ASIA] class A) transplanted with olfactory mucosa autograft of stem-like progenitor cells for neural repair. After grafts, MRI showed partial to moderate filling of lesion sites. 2 patients restored sensation in their bladder, and one of these regained voluntary contraction of anal sphincter. 100% of patients had improvement in ASIA motor scores: mean of 6.3 in upper extremities for 3 tetraplegic subjects and mean of 3.9 in lower extremities for 4 paraplegic subjects. The side effects included transient pain relieved with medication and sensory decrease in one patient, probably caused by difficulty in locating the lesion [94]. Autologous transplantation of olfactory ensheathing cells (OECs) was performed into the spinal cord in 6 patients with complete, thoracic paraplegia, followed for 3 years. 1 patient showed an improvement over 3 segments in light touch and pin prick sensitivity bilaterally, anteriorly and posteriorly [96].</p>

Table-3	
Huntington's disease (HD) Associated with death of projection neurons in the caudate-putamen (striatum) [97].	A patient with HD died 18 months after transplantation of human fetal striatal tissue from cardiovascular disease. Postmortem histological analysis revealed surviving transplanted cells with typical morphology of the developing striatum. No histological evidence of rejection was observed. Fetal neural cells without mutant HD may be able to replace damaged host neurons and reconstitute damaged neuronal connections [98].
Brain Stroke	10 stroke patients received a subarachnoidal injection of cell suspension containing immature nervous and hematopoietic tissue. 6 months after engraftment, functional activity significantly increased in contrast to the control group. No serious side effects were observed [99]. Bang et al randomly allocated 30 patients with infarcts within the middle cerebral arterial territory and neurological deficits into 1 of 3 groups: the MSC group (5 patients) received intravenous infusion of 1×10^8 autologous MSCs, whereas the control group (25 patients) did not receive MSCs. The patients were followed up for 1 year. Outcomes improved in MSC-treated group compared with control group: Barthel index, to evaluate neurological deficits, ($p=0.011, 0.017$ and 0.115 at 3, 6 and 12 months, respectively) and modified Rankin score, to evaluate function, ($p=0.086, 0.171$ and 0.286 at 3, 6 and 12 months, respectively) of MSC patients improved consistently during the follow-up period. No adverse cell-related, serological or imaging-defined effects were observed [100].
Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD)	Autologous transplantation of muscle-derived CD133+ cells was used in in boys with DMD in a 7-month, double-blind trial. SC safety was tested by measuring muscle strength & evaluating muscle structures with MRI and histological analysis. Timed cardiac and pulmonary function tests were secondary outcome measures. No local or systemic side effects were observed in all treated DMD patients. Treated patients had an increased ratio of capillary per muscle fibers with a switch from slow to fast myosin-positive myofibers[101]. 10 boys with DMD & absent dystrophin (age 5-10 years) were implanted with 100 million myoblasts in the anterior tibial muscle of one leg and placebo in the other. Cyclosporine (5 mg/kg/day) was administered for 7 months. Pre and post-implantation (after 1 and 6 months) muscle biopsies were analyzed. Force generation (tetanic tension and maximum voluntary contraction) was measured monthly in a double-blind design. There was increased force generation in both legs of all boys. Using the polymerase chain reaction, evidence of myoblast survival and dystrophin mRNA expression was obtained in 3 patients after 1 month and in 1 patient after 6 months [104].
DMD)	Mendell et al injected 110 million muscle cells donated by fathers or brothers once a month for 6 months to the biceps brachii muscles of one arm of 12 boys with DMD. The opposite arms served as sham-injected controls. Strength was measured by quantitative isometric muscle testing. Six months after the final myoblast transfer, there was no significant difference in muscle strength between arms injected with myoblasts and sham-injected arms. In one patient, 10.3 percent of muscle fibers expressed donor-derived dystrophin after myoblast transfer. Three other patients also had a low level of donor dystrophin (< 1 percent); eight had none [105]. One biceps muscle of 8 patients with DMD was injected at 55 sites with 55 million normal myoblasts from fathers. The other biceps of each patient was injected with a placebo as a control. All patients received cyclophosphamide for immunosuppression for 6 or 12 months. No serious complications were observed. The overall therapeutic efficiency was poor [106]. 5 young boys with DMD were treated with injection of the biceps with myoblasts. At the same time, myoblasts were also injected in the left tibialis anterior (TA) of these patients. The strength developed during maximal static contractions of the elbow flexor and extensor muscles was measured with a Kin-Com dynamometer. No increase in static elbow flexion torque was measured at any time from 2 mo up to 18 mo after the transplantation[107].

Table(4):Cirrhosis trials summary	
9 alcoholic liver cirrhosis patients were treated with infusion of autologous BM derived CD34+ Treatment was well tolerated and no side effects were observed. Serum bilirubin significantly decreased ($p<0.05$) 4, 8, and 12 week post-infusion. Liver enzymes levels improved through the study. The Child-Pugh score (CP; used to assess the prognosis of chronic liver disease) improved in 7 out of 9 patient, while 5 patients had improvement in ascites in imaging[120].	
9 liver cirrhosis cases treated with autologous BM cell infusion Significantly improved Child-Pugh scores were seen at 4 and 24 weeks ($p<0.05$). Alpha-Fetoprotein& proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA) expression in liver biopsy tissue was significantly elevated after ABMI therapy ($p < .05$). No major adverse effects were noted [121].	
10 patients with chronic liver disease received autologous BMCs infusion. All patients were discharged 48 h after BMC infusion. 2 patients developed mild pain at the BM needle puncture site. Bilirubin levels were lower at 1&4 months after treatment than baseline levels . Albumin levels 4 months after BMC infusion (3.73 ± 0.5) were higher than baseline levels (3.47 ± 0.5). International normalized ratio (INR) decreased from 1.48 (SD = 0.23) to 1.43 (SD = 0.23) one month after treatment[122].	
3 patients with large central liver malignancies were treated with intra-portal administration of autologous CD133(+) BMSCs. 2.5-fold increase in mean proliferation rates was noted compared with a 3 patients treated without application of BMSCs. Portovenous application of CD133(+) BMSCs could be a novel therapeutic approach of enhancing and accelerating hepatic regeneration [123].	

Malignancy	
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	Patients with renal cell carcinoma (RCC) treated with reduced intensity conditioning and peripheral blood stem cells and immunosuppression experienced chronic GVHD in 33%. Transplant-related mortality was 16% at one year. Complete (n = 4) or partial (n = 24) responses. Factors associated with survival included chronic GVHD. Patients (n = 17) with chronic GVHD and given DLI had a 2-year survival of 70% [124]. HSCT leads to durable responses in a minority of metastatic RCC patients. Appropriate patient selection is paramount. Anemia and decreased performance status may enable risk stratification [125,126]. Treatment of metastatic RCC with HSCT after conditioning with immunosuppression was associated with a graft-versus-tumor effect [127].
Breast cancer	The use of first-line high-dose chemotherapy (HDC) with AHCT have some effect on overall survival (OS), disease-free survival (DFS) and response rate in patients with metastatic breast cancer responding to induction therapy [128,129].
	Allogeneic SC transplantation (allo-SCT) can induce curative graft-versus-leukemia reactions for hematological malignancies through allogeneic immunity. As the gastrointestinal tract is a target of graft-versus host disease (GvHD), colorectal cancer has been suggested as a candidate for allo-SCT. [130]. Some studies described the feasibility of combination of chemotherapy and SCT for the treatment of ovarian malignancies. [131]

Therapeutic applications

The stem cells isolated from adult tissues are a non-controversial source of stem cells for therapy. They are “plastic” and thus could transdifferentiate into stem cells committed for various non-hematopoietic organs and tissues [39]. Several reports demonstrated the remarkable regenerative potential of hematopoietic stem cells (HSC) in animal models, for example, after heart infarct [40], stroke [41], spinal cord injury [42] and liver damage [43]. However since these first exciting and promising reports, the role of BM-derived HSC in the repair of damaged organs has become controversial [44, 45]. Further experiments with highly purified populations of HSC showed them not to be effective in regenerating damaged heart [46] or brain [47]. The degree of stem cell plasticity and the potential contribution of bone marrow (BM)-, mobilized peripheral blood (mPB)- or cord blood (CB-derived) stem cells to organ regeneration remain unknown as these tissues may contain heterogeneous populations of stem cells [44,48].

Mesenchymal Stem Cells (Multipotent Mesenchymal Stromal Cells)—MSC are

fibroblastic cells that are essential in forming the hematopoietic microenvironment in which HSC grow and differentiate [49]. These cells contribute to the regeneration of mesenchymal tissues (e.g., bone, cartilage, muscle, ligament, tendon, adipose and stroma) [50]. It is likely that MSC may be contaminated by other populations of primitive non-hematopoietic stem cells. This possibility should be considered whenever a “trans-dedifferentiation” of MSC into cells from other germ layers is demonstrated. Because various inconsistencies have come to light in the field of MSC research, the International Society for Cellular Therapy recently recommended avoiding the name of MSC stem cells and changing it to multipotent

mesenchymal stromal cells instead [51]. The phenotype of these cells.

Multipotent Adult Progenitor Cells (MAPC)—MAPC are isolated from BM as well from various adult organs as a population of CD45- GPA-A- adherent cells and they display a similar fibroblastic morphology to MSC. Interestingly MAPC are the only population of BM derived stem cells that, so far as is known, contribute to all three germ layers after injection into a developing blastocyst, indicating their pluripotency [25]. The contribution of MAPC to blastocyst development, however, requires confirmation by other, independent laboratories.

Marrow-isolated adult multi-lineage inducible (MIAMI) cells—This population of cells was isolated from human adult BM by culturing BM MNC in low oxygen tension conditions on fibronectin [52]. MIAMI cells were isolated from the BM of people ranging from 3- to 72-years old. Colonies derived from MIAMI cells expressed several markers for cells from all three germ layers, suggesting that, at least as determined by in vitro assays, they are endowed with pluripotency. However, these cells have not been tested so far for their ability to complete blastocyst development. The potential relationship of these cells to MSC and MAPC described above is not clear, although it is possible that these are overlapping populations of cells identified by slightly different isolation/expansion strategies.

Multipotent Adult Stem Cells (MACS)-These cells express pluripotent-state-specific

transcriptions factors (Oct-4, Nanog and Rex1) and were cloned from human liver, heart and BM-isolated mononuclear cells [53]. MACS display a high telomerase activity and exhibit a wide range of differentiation potential. Again the potential relationship of these cells to MSC, MAPC and MIAMI described above is not clear, although it is possible that these are overlapping populations of cells

identified by slightly different isolation/expansion strategies

STEM CELL CLINICAL TRIALS

Several trials have been conducted on treatment of **Autoimmune diseases and Neurological disorders**. with autologous HSCs transplantation (AHSCT) as summarized in Table-2 and implantation of embryonic and adult SCs as summarized in Table-3 [54-100]. Myoblast transfer has also been tried in muscle dystrophies [101-107]. Fassa set al noted the risk of development post-transplantation autoimmune disease. In 35 patients, one presented autoimmune thyroiditis 11 months

Patients with acute MI received an intracoronary infusion of progenitor cells derive from bone marrow showed at 4 months improvement in LVEF which was significantly greater than in the placebo group At 1 year, intracoronary infusion of BMCs was associated with a reduction in the pre-specified combined clinical endpoint of death, recurrence of Myocardial infarction, and any revascularization procedure (P=0.01) [109]. Patients with previous MI and ejection fraction (EF) $\leq 35\%$ received autologous skeletal myoblast transplantation and bypass surgery. New York Heart Association (NYHA) class improved from 2.5 to 1.8 at 1 month (p=0.004 versus baseline) and EF increased from 24.3 to 31 at M1 (p=0.001 versus baseline) and remained stable thereafter implantation [110]. Patients survived acute MI and underwent to coronary artery by-pass grafting were treated with the isolation of autologous myoblasts from biopsy and them injection, after amplification. LVEF increased from 25% to 40% before the procedure to 29% to 47% during the 4-month visit (p<0.05), and the effects was maintained throughout all the follow-up in some patients [111].

No obvious beneficial effect of and intracoronary transfer of autologous BMCs 4-8 days after percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) in patients with acute MI compared with patients received optimum post-infarction medical treatment. Left-ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) increased by 0.7 percentage points in the control group and 6.7 percentage points in the BMC group (p=0.0026). In transplanted group, enhanced left-ventricular systolic function primarily in myocardial segments adjacent to the infarcted

after transplant and another developed a refractory, acquired hemophilia A which resulted in death 28 months post-transplant [58].

Studies suggested that SC could improve heart function and repair cardiac tissue after myocardial infarction (MI). Patients with MI and left ventricular (LV) dysfunction indicated for coronary surgery treated with myoblast growth from skeletal muscle biopsy experienced no improvement in LV function compared with placebo. However, the high-dose SC treatment was associated with significant LV volumes compare with placebo. No significantly difference of major cardiac adverse events and ventricular arrhythmias was observed between treated groups ad placebo. [108].

area. No augmented risk of adverse clinical events, in-stent re-stenosis, or pro-arrhythmic effects [112].

Ocular surface disease are characterized by persistent epithelial defects, corneal vascularisation, chronic inflammation, scarring and conjunctivalisation, resulting in visual loss. This pathology is associated to limbal stem cell deficiency (LSCD), and consequently the lack of ability to produce new epithelial cells and to restore function. LSCD can be caused by a variety of hereditary or acquired disorders [113].

Treatment of patients with LSCD caused by burns with autologous limbal stem cell obtained by controlateral eye and cultured on fibrin were reported to be successful. Re-epithelialization occurred within the first week. Inflammation and vascularisation regressed within the first 3-4 weeks. By the first month, the corneal surface was covered by a transparent, normal-looking epithelium. At 12-27 months follow-up, corneal surfaces were clinically and cytologically stable. Successful endothelial rejection in central penetrating graft after simultaneous keratolimbal allograft transplantation (KLAT) and penetrating keratoplasty (PKP) using the same donor cornea has also been reported in few patients. Several patients with various ocular disorders Stevens-Johnson syndrome, ectodermal dysplasia, chemical injury, ocular cicatricial pemphigoid, and keratoconjunctivitis treated with limbal allograft transplantation experienced restoration of the corneal epithelium and decreased vascularisation. Corneal opacification was reduced eyes and visual improvement was achieved in several eyes. [114-119].

Cirrhosis is irreversible once it occurs, and treatment generally focuses on preventing progression and complications. In advanced stages of cirrhosis the only feasible option is a liver transplant. An alternative solution for end stage liver failure could be stem cell therapy Table-4 summarized trial results.

Malignancies

Allogenic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation is often used to treat hematological malignancies. The efficacy of this procedure is due to both myeloablative conditioning and graft-versus-leukemia (GVL). Allogenic transplantation has been developed to treat solid tumors, with the expectation that graft-versus-tumor (GVT), like GVL, will have a significant anti-tumor effect. This effect has been demonstrated in renal carcinomas, and with less evidence in breast cancers.

Five patients with malignant ovarian tumors resistant to chemotherapy underwent allogenic transplantation, four from bone marrow, and one from peripheral blood stem cells. All donors were HLA-identical siblings. One patient received a myeloablative conditioning regimen, while the other four received a non-myeloablative regimen. Two patients received donor lymphocyte infusions (DLI). Four of the patients presented with acute or chronic GVHD associated with tumor regression of at least 50%. These tumor regressions were measured by CA-125 levels and CT scans. The fifth patient died of rapid progression just after transplantation. Of the four transplantation survivors, three received a non-myeloablative regimen which did not seem to reduce treatment effectiveness. While it did reduce toxicity, one of these patients died of GVHD after 127 days. DLI was administered to two patients. These infusions seemed to promote GVHD which was able to control disease progression for one patient and had no apparent effect on the other. **Allograft of hematopoietic stem cells might be of interest in ovarian cancer.** The results in one patient also suggest that DLI may be an effective immunotherapy, although doses and timing need to be determined. The number of cases presented is small [132].

Since 1980, 75 patients with **small-cell lung cancer (SCLC)** have been enrolled in four consecutive studies of high-dose chemotherapy using autologous bone marrow transplantation (ABMT) to assist hematological recovery. In the

first study, 25 patients were treated with cyclophosphamide (160-200 mg/kg) as the sole chemotherapy; in the second (26 patients), the cycle of high-dose cyclophosphamide (with or without 800-1,200 mg/m² etoposide) was repeated as induction treatment. In the first study, response was high [14 complete responses (CR), 7 partial responses (PR)] but was not increased by repeating the cycle (15 CR, 8 PR), and survival was slightly worse in the second trial. In the third study, 15 patients were treated with doxorubicin, vincristine and etoposide for two cycles and then with 200 mg/kg cyclophosphamide. Although high-dose cyclophosphamide increased the complete response rate, the additional responses were short-lived. In the final study, an attempt was made to increase the initial CR rate by combination chemotherapy using carboplatin (400-600 mg/m²), etoposide (120 mg/m² x 4) and either high-dose cyclophosphamide (40 mg/kg x 4) or melphalan (140 mg/m²). Although all nine patients responded, none underwent a CR. The long-term survival (up to 7 years) does not appear to be different from that in comparably selected cases treated with conventional chemotherapy[133].

A multi-centric randomized prospective trial was conducted to test whether late intensification chemotherapy would increase the emission rate, the relapse-free survival, and the survival of small-cell lung cancer patients responding to induction chemotherapy. Autologous bone marrow transplantation was used as support to reduce the duration of the aplasia induced by very high-dose chemotherapy. As induction chemotherapy, 101 patients received, during a period of 5 months, a total dosage of 120 mg/m² methotrexate, 4.5 mg/m² vincristine, 1,800 mg/m² cyclophosphamide, 180 mg/m² doxorubicin, 160 mg/m² cisplatin, 750 mg/m² VP-16-213, and 30 Gy prophylactic cranial irradiation. Forty-five patients, selected for their sensitivity to this induction treatment, were randomized to a last cycle of chemotherapy that combined cyclophosphamide, BCNU, and VP-16-213 either at a conventional dosage of 750 mg/m² intravenously (IV), 60 mg/m² IV, and 600 mg/m² orally or alternatively at a very high dosage of 6 g/m² IV, 300 mg/m² IV, and 500 mg/m² IV, respectively. In the late intensification group, the complete remission rate increased from 39% before randomization to 79% after high-dose chemotherapy. Median relapse-free survivals after randomization for intensified and control chemotherapy groups were 28 and 10 weeks,

respectively ($P = .002$). Median overall survival after induction therapy was 68 weeks for the intensified group compared with 55 weeks for the conventional therapy group ($P = .13$). Four patients died during intensification. Patients in both groups relapsed at the primary site. It can thus be concluded that late intensification chemotherapy for sensitive small-cell lung cancer increases the complete remission rate and resulted in a statistically significant increase in the relapse-free survival. However, since relapse occurred at the primary site and toxicity was high, overall survival was not significantly improved[134].

To determine progression-free survival (PFS) and overall long-term survival for limited-stage small-cell lung cancer (SCLC) patients aged 60 years or younger who respond to first-line chemotherapy followed by high-dose combination alkylating agents (cyclophosphamide 5,625 mg/m², cisplatin 165 mg/m², and carmustine 480 mg/m²) with hematologic stem cell support and chest and prophylactic cranial radiotherapy. Patients were selected on the basis of their continued response to first-line therapy, their relative lack of significant co-morbidity, and their ability to obtain financial clearance. Of 36 patients with stage III SCLC, nine patients (25%) had achieved a complete response (CR), 20 had achieved a near-CR, and seven had achieved a partial response before undergoing high-dose therapy. Toxicity included three deaths (8%). For all patients, the median PFS was 21 months. The 2- and 5-year survival rates after dose intensification were 53% (95% confidence interval [CI], 39% to 72%), and 41% (95% CI, 28% to 61%). Of the 29 patients who were in or near CR before undergoing high-dose therapy, 14 remain continuously progression-free a median of 61 months (range, 40 to 139 months) after high-dose therapy. Actuarial 2- and 5-year PFS rates were 57% (95% CI, 41% to 79%) and 53% (95% CI, 38% to 76%). By multivariate analysis, short intensive induction chemotherapy was associated with favorable outcome ($P < .05$)[135].

Combined-modality treatment for limited-disease small cell lung cancer using conventional chemotherapy and chest irradiation achieves high response rates, but most patients relapse over a period of 12 to 16 months. To improve current results, we performed a phase II trial including high-dose chemotherapy and peripheral blood progenitor cell transplantation (PBPCT) as part of an early intensification strategy after two cycles of induction therapy. Moreover, to reduce the risk of local recurrence, the protocol

included surgical resection in stages I to IIIA patients as well as chest irradiation. Between January 1991 and July 1994, 16 consecutive patients (median age, 50 years; age range, 30 to 59 years) were treated in this single-center trial. The patients received two cycles of conventional chemotherapy consisting of etoposide 500 mg/m², ifosfamide 4 g/m², cisplatin 50 mg/m², and epirubicin 50 mg/m² plus granulocyte colony-stimulating factor 5 microg/kg at a 3-week interval, followed by PBPCT collection and subsequent high-dose etoposide 1,500 mg/m², ifosfamide 12 g/m², carboplatin 750 mg/m², and epirubicin 150 mg/m² with PBPCT. The duration of the entire chemotherapy program was 9 weeks. Six of 10 patients in stages I to IIIA and one of six patients in stage IIIB received adjuvant surgery before high-dose chemotherapy, followed by thoracic (50 Gy) and prophylactic (30 Gy) cranial irradiation. Hematopoietic reconstitution after high-dose chemotherapy occurred within 11 days (range, 9 to 17 days) for both neutrophils ($>0.5 \times 10^9/L$) and platelets ($>20 \times 10^9/L$). Oral mucositis (World Health Organization grade 2 to 4) was the predominant nonhematologic toxicity, which was observed in 12 of 16 patients. One patient developed neutropenic septicemia with fatal multi-organ failure. At a median follow-up of 44 months (range, 32 to 77 months) after PBPCT, nine patients are alive and well, resulting in a disease-free and overall survival rate of 56.3% \pm 12.4%. The median overall survival has not yet been achieved. None of the patients who had surgery relapsed or died after therapy. All relapses occurred within the first 12 months after PBPCT. Patients in stages I to IIIA (10 patients) had a 70% \pm 14% overall survival rate at 4 years, while patients in stage IIIB (six patients) had a 33% \pm 19% survival rate at 4 years, with a median survival of 17 months post transplant. These data demonstrate that a multi-modality treatment including early high-dose chemotherapy with PBPCT may lead to a prolonged disease-free survival in the majority of patients. A randomized phase III study has now been initiated to prospectively investigate the role of high-dose chemotherapy, surgery, and chest irradiation in the multidisciplinary approach to limited-disease small cell lung cancer[136].

A phase I-II trial assessed the feasibility and activity of a combination chemotherapy regimen with etoposide, ifosfamide, cisplatin or carboplatin, and epirubicin in limited-disease (LD, stages I-IIIB) and extensive-stage (ED, stage IV) small-cell lung cancer (SCLC). Standard-dose chemotherapy (SDC)

consisting of etoposide (500 mg/m²), ifosfamide (4000 mg/m²), cisplatin (50 mg/m²) and epirubicin (50 mg/m²) (VIP-E), followed by granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (G-CSF), was given to 100 patients with SCLC. Thirty patients with qualifying responses to VIP-E proceeded to high-dose chemotherapy (HDC) with autologous peripheral blood stem-cell transplantation (PBSCT) after etoposide (1,500 mg/m²), ifosfamide (12,000 mg/m²), carboplatin (750 mg/m²) and epirubicin (150 mg/m²) (VIC-E) conditioning. For standard-dose vip-e: ninety-seven patients were evaluable for response. The objective response rate was 81% in LD SCLC (33% CR, 48% PR; excluding patients in surgical CR) and 77% in ED SCLC (18% CR, 58% PR). The treatment-related mortality (TRM) of SDC was 2%. Two additional patients in CR from their SCLC developed secondary non-small-cell lung cancers (NSCLC), and both were cured by surgery. The median survival was 19 months in LD SCLC and 6 months in ED SCLC. The five-year survivals were 36% in LD and 0% in ED SCLC. For high-dose vic-e: HDC was feasible in 16% of ED-, and 58% of LD-patients. All HDC patients (n = 30) improved or maintained prior responses. Four patients died of early treatment-related complications (TRM 13%). Two additional patients in CR from their SCLC developed secondary malignancies (esophageal cancer, secondary chronic myelogenous leukemia). The median survivals were 26 months in LD SCLC, and 8 months in ED SCLC. The five-year survival was 50% in LD and 0% in ED SCLC[137].

To determine the feasibility and safety of multiple sequential courses of high-dose chemotherapy and peripheral-blood progenitor cells (PBPCs) administered in a multicenter setting to patients with small-cell lung cancer. Sixty-nine patients (limited disease, n = 30; extensive disease, n = 39) treated at 15 European centers were scheduled to receive three courses of high-dose chemotherapy with ifosfamide 10 g/m², carboplatin 1200 mg/m², and etoposide 1200 mg/m² (ICE) divided over 4 days at 28-day intervals. PBPCs were harvested before treatment and mobilized with epirubicin 150 mg/m² administered via an intravenous bolus divided over 2 days and filgrastim 5 microg/kg/d administered subcutaneously. The performed leukaphereses (one to five per patient) yielded a median of 16.6 x 10⁶/kg (range, 1.0 to 96.6 x 10⁶/kg) CD34(+) cells, which was sufficient for three re-infusions. Fifty patients (72%) completed the treatment according to schedule. Nine patients completed two courses, and six patients completed

one course of treatment. The increase in dose-intensity was 290% that of a standard ICE regimen. The median duration of myelosuppression was similar between courses, namely 4 days (range, 1 to 12 days) for leukocytes less than 0.5 x 10⁹/L and 4 days (range, 0 to 22 days) for thrombocytes less than 20 x 10⁹/L. Febrile neutropenia developed in 66% of courses, severe diarrhea in 14%, mucositis in 10%, and nausea and vomiting in 21% of courses. There were six cases of toxic death (9%), most of which occurred in the first year of accrual and thus were attributable to the learning curve. The antitumor effect of the regimen was reflected in an 86% remission rate (95% confidence interval [CI], 74% to 93%), with 51% of patients achieving a complete response (95% CI, 38% to 63%). Median overall survival was 18 months for patients with limited disease and 11 months for patients with extensive disease [138].

RISKS OF STEM CELL THERAPY

Hepatic veno-occlusive disease or veno-occlusive disease (VOD) is one of the most frequent complications after stem cell transplantation. It is a complication of high-dose chemotherapy given before a bone marrow transplant. [139]. Respiratory complications are other typology of side effect. In fact, the major limitations to the successful use of HSC transplantation include respiratory complications and graft versus host disease. Lung dysfunction occurs in up to 50% of subjects after HSC transplantation, and pulmonary complications are among the most common causes of morbidity and mortality after this procedure.

Obliterative bronchiolitis (OB) is a multifactorial process involving both alloimmunologic and non-alloimmunologic reactions. Usually OB develops as a late complication (after the first 100 days) of HSC transplantation. Clinical data suggest that non-alloimmunologic inflammatory conditions such as viral infections, recurrent aspiration, and conditioning chemo-radiotherapy may also play a role in the pathogenesis of OB after HSC transplantation. [140,141].

Bronchiolitis obliterans organizing pneumonia (BOOP). Although the pathogenesis of BOOP following HSCT is poorly understood, involvement of an allo-immunologic reaction has been again considered. In animal studies, BOOP develops following infection with reovirus, and a significant role for T cells and Th1-derived cytokines, including interferon- α , was

implicated in the development of disease [142,143]. In other non-HSCT settings BOOP has been seen in association with infection, drugs, radiation therapy, and a number of connective tissue disorders [144] A trial where 33 patients randomly submitted to either AHSCT or selected CD34+ didn't show any advantage with antigen selection, but confirm immunomodulatory action of HSC in joint microenvironment [145].

EBMT registry identified 34 patients with severe JIA treated with to BM harvest, positive stem cells selection, T cells depletion and re-infusion. 18 patients had a complete remission of JIA, 6 patients had a partial remission while 7 hadn't remission. 70% of subjects develop at least one infection, mainly during the aplastic period. 3 patients died after transplantation of infections complications. The protocol could be improved by prophylactic administration of antiviral drugs and intravenous immunoglobulin until immune system return competent [146].

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